

Effect of cytokinins on shoot proliferation.^a

Phytohormone (2 mg/liter)	Initial shoots (no.)	First subculture		Second subculture		Third subculture	
		Shoots (no.)	Shoot proliferation (%)	Shoots (no.)	Shoot proliferation (%)	Shoots (no.)	Shoot proliferation (%)
Benzylamino- purine (BAP)	48	139	289.6	498	358.3	1632	327.7
Kinetin	38	74	194.7	184	248.6	475	258.2
Zeatin	73	101	138.4	189	187.1	430	227.5

^aSubculture interval = 4 wk.

The medium supplemented with BAP produces the best response for shoot proliferation (see table). A test of differ-

ent concentrations of BAP showed that 2 mg BAP/liter is optimum for shoot proliferation. When the concentration of

BAP is increased to 4 mg/liter, there are some shoots with abnormal plant type and unfavorable leaf color even though the proliferation rate is reasonably high. After getting enough shoots by subculture, the proliferated shoots can be separated and transferred onto rooting medium, on which almost all of the shoots grow roots. About 1,000 regenerated plantlets were transferred into soil in the summer. Visual observation showed all plants to be normal. ■

Greenhouse rearing and rating scale for rice mealy bug

R. Velusamy and S. Jeyarani, Entomology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India; and R. C. Saxena, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE), Kenya

Rice mealy bug *Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger possesses behavioral attributes that made earlier attempts for mass-rearing in the greenhouse unsuccessful: a) at all stages (except crawler), the pests are sedentary and remain under the leaf sheath, making their handling tedious and time consuming; b) the soft-bodied females are sensitive to handling and do not settle on plants if disturbed; and c) insect longevity, fecundity, and population increase are

significantly influenced by host plant age.

Based on these observations, we developed a procedure for mass-rearing *B. rehi* in the greenhouse (see figure). Using an adhesive (Camilin), five gravid females were attached to the auricles of potted 60-d-old TN1 plants at the rate of one female/tiller. The plants were then covered with a mylar film cage (90 cm high, 10 cm diam). By 25 d after infesta-

tion (25 DAI), about 360 adult females were produced on each potted plant, and 5 d later, crawlers emerged. Gravid females collected from leaf sheaths were

Procedure for greenhouse rearing of rice mealy bug and screening of rice cultivars for resistance.

Reactions of rice varieties to *B. rehi* in the bulk seedling test.

Variety	Plant damage rating ^a	
Co 9	3	d
Co 18	1	e
Co 21	1	e
Co 22	1	e
Co 23	5	c
Co 25	7	b
Co 26	9	a
Co 27	9	a
Ptb18	9	a
Ptb21	1	e
Ptb33	3	d
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	a

^aAv of 5 replications. See text for definition of scale. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

held in a petri dish lined with moist filter paper and used for infesting plants. Crawlers that emerged were used for greenhouse screening of rice cultivars.

To screen for resistance, pregerminated seeds of 12 rice varieties were sown in seedboxes laid out in a randomized complete block design and replicated five times. When seedlings were 7 d old, the seedboxes were placed in a water-filled galvanized iron tray and

infested with 5-6 crawlers/seedling. TN1 plants loaded with crawlers from the stock culture were held horizontally above the seedboxes and tapped gently so that crawlers were dislodged and distributed uniformly on the test seedlings.

At 20 DAI when about 90% of susceptible check TN1 plants were dead, the varieties were rated for plant damage on a 0-9 scale where 0 = no damage, 1 = slight damage, 3 = first and second leaves

of most plants partially browning, 5 = pronounced browning and stunting or about half of the plants wilting or dead, 7 = more than half of the plants wilted or dead and the remaining plants severely stunted and covered with a mealy coating, and 9 = all plants dead. Plants with negligible damage were considered resistant. Using this test, varieties Co 18, Co 21, Co 22, and Ptb21 were rated resistant (see table). ■

News about research collaboration

Identifying factors in yield decline

A new method to isolate specific fractions of soil organic matter (SOM) has been developed by IRRI scientists investigating the causes of yield decline that occurs in many long-term experiments on intensive, irrigated rice systems in the tropics. SOM represents the largest soil reservoir of soil nitrogen, and release of nitrogen from the SOM pool supplies

much of the nitrogen required by the rice crop.

A puzzling aspect of the yield decline is that the amount of nitrogen supplied by soil decreases over time despite the conservation or even increase in SOM. Unlike most other crops which are grown in aerated soil, rice is mostly grown in flooded soil in lowland ricefields.

With funding from the United States Agency for International Development, IRRI scientists Dan Olk and Ken

Cassman are trying to determine if changes in the chemical structure of SOM can help explain the decrease in soil N supply that occurs without a corresponding reduction in SOM content.

Olk and Cassman believe that chemical characterization of these SOM fractions will help identify the factors contributing to the yield decline and will increase understanding of soil quality and sustainability of intensive rice systems. ■

A new rainfed lowland rice research institute in India

A new rice research institute will soon rise in Assam, India's most northeasterly state. The institute, supported by a project under development by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, will be dedicated to research in the rainfed ecosystems of eastern India.

Assam has a total rice area of about 2.4 million ha, 90% of which are rainfed. About 2 million ha of its rice area are flooded every year and an average of more than 300,000 ha of rice are destroyed due to flooding. Assam is flood-prone because Meghalaya and Chirapunji receive the highest rainfall in the world, more than 5,000 mm each year; and Assam has the world's largest river island, the Majuli Island.

The 25-ha rainfed lowland rice research station will focus on flood-prone environments. Emphasis will be placed on submergence tolerance of rice. Institutions and key scientists from all states of eastern India will be involved. ■

Extensive rice research training program in Lao PDR

One of the most serious constraints to improving agriculture in the Lao People's Democratic Republic has been the lack of adequate research capacity to support increased food production—especially for rice, the country's staple cereal.

With a rapidly increasing population coupled with land degradation in the uplands, improvements in Lao PDR's rice production systems are urgently needed. Rice production in the country is among the lowest in Asia. In each of the past 5 years, Lao PDR had to import 30,000-40,000 tons of rice.

IRRI, with support from the Swiss Development Cooperation (SDC), is helping Lao PDR develop its national rice research program. "Because of the scope and intensity of the training effort, the impact on the national research system is enormous," says Dr. Glenn L. Denning, head of IRRI's International Programs Management Office.

More than 350 Lao scientists have participated in training at IRRI since

1991 through a special program supported by SDC. The scientists were trained in subjects including integrated pest management, training of trainers, sustainable rice farming systems, gender analysis, and rice germplasm collection and conservation.

A three-year, US\$3.54 million grant from SDC will continue the extensive efforts of IRRI and the country to expand rice research to cover all of the significant rice-growing provinces and to increase the number of agricultural researchers and technicians trained in rice production. Training activities will be accelerated inside Lao PDR, at IRRI headquarters, and in other countries, including Thailand. ■